

Assessing Digital Literacy and Utilization of Library Resources among Undergraduate Students in Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti

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Abstract

This study examined the digital literacy skills and utilization of library resources among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti. In the rapidly digitalizing academic environment, university libraries now provide both physical and electronic resources to support learning and research. Despite these developments, many students still rely heavily on internet search engines and lecture materials, resulting in the underutilization of library resources. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Data were collected from 405 undergraduate students selected through stratified random sampling across faculties and academic levels using a structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that 90.4% of students effectively use digital devices for academic tasks, while only 52.6% are comfortable using essential academic software such as word processing applications. The study also found that 71.8% frequently use the internet for academic research, although many students experience information overload. Furthermore, 98.3% regularly visit the library, but concerns persist regarding accessibility and adequacy of resources. Factors such as digital literacy competence, accessibility, and lecturer recommendations significantly influence library resource utilization. The study concludes that gaps in advanced digital literacy skills limit effective utilization of academic resources. It recommends targeted digital literacy training, improved library collections, and stronger integration of library resources into teaching and learning activities.

Keywords: *Digital literacy, Library resource utilization, Academic libraries, Digital resources, Digital tools proficiency.*

Introduction

In an era characterized by rapid technological advancement and digitalization, the role of libraries in higher education has undergone substantial transformation. The advent of digital technologies has revolutionized the way information is accessed, disseminated, and utilized across academic environments. Consequently, libraries have evolved from traditional repositories of printed materials into hybrid knowledge centres that integrate both physical and digital resources to support teaching, learning, and research. In this evolving context, digital literacy has become a critical competency for effectively engaging with information in the digital age, particularly among students who are increasingly dependent on technology for academic activities.

For students striving for academic excellence, access to both printed and online resources remains indispensable for effective research and learning within the university system. These resources are essential in enhancing students' information literacy skills and supporting their academic development. However, existing literature indicates a growing preference among contemporary students, often described as digital natives or digital millennials, for digital forms of information consumption (Boakye, 2018; Iivari, Sharma & Ventä-Olkkonen, 2020). Despite this preference, studies have shown that many students lack the necessary digital literacy skills required to effectively navigate, evaluate, and utilize digital information resources available in academic libraries (Igbo, 2020).

Empirical evidence further suggests that a significant proportion of undergraduate students struggle to effectively utilize digital library collections to meet their academic and research needs. Library professionals have also observed that many students tend to prioritize non-academic internet use over engagement with library resources, thereby reducing the academic impact of available information services. This indicates a persistent gap between resource availability and actual utilization for scholarly purposes.

In addition, anecdotal and empirical reports highlight a continued underutilization of library facilities among undergraduate students, despite the availability of both digital and print resources (Martin-Yeboah & Atuase, 2019). This situation raises concerns about the effectiveness of library services in supporting students' academic work and suggests that access alone does not guarantee meaningful usage. The gap may be linked to inadequate digital literacy skills, lack of awareness of available resources, or insufficient training in information-seeking strategies.

In response to the demands of the digital age, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has significantly transformed how individuals communicate, learn, read, and interact with information. Humans, in adapting to these changes, have developed various skills to function effectively in digital environments. These competencies are collectively referred to as digital literacy. Yasemin (2018) describes digital literacy as the ability to adapt and function effectively in a technology-driven society, while Oriogu, Subair, Oriogu-Ogbuiyi, and Ogbuiyi (2017) define it as a set of skills that enable individuals to efficiently perform information retrieval and

processing tasks in digital environments. Digital literacy therefore includes the ability to locate, evaluate, synthesize, and communicate information using digital technologies effectively.

A digitally literate individual is expected to critically evaluate and effectively use information from credible online sources. Despite the increasing availability of digital resources in academic libraries, studies indicate that undergraduate students often underutilize these resources, relying instead on general internet search engines and course lecture notes. Factors influencing the utilization of library resources include familiarity with library systems, perceived relevance of materials, ease of access, and level of digital literacy competence.

Libraries have responded to these changes by evolving into dynamic information centres that provide access to e-books, online journals, databases, and multimedia resources, as well as offering services such as virtual reference support and online learning platforms. However, the extent to which students possess the required digital literacy skills to fully exploit these resources remains unclear, particularly within specific institutional contexts such as Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti

Despite the expansion of digital library services and increasing emphasis on ICT integration in higher education, there remains limited empirical evidence on the actual level of digital literacy skills among undergraduate students and how these skills influence their utilization of library resources in Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti. Furthermore, the specific factors that influence both digital literacy development and library resource usage in this context have not been sufficiently explored. This gap in knowledge limits the ability of universities and library administrators to design targeted interventions that enhance effective resource utilization and digital competence among students.

Against this background, this study investigates the digital literacy skills and utilization of library resources among undergraduate students of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti. Specifically, it examines students' level of digital literacy, their patterns of library resource usage, and the factors influencing both digital literacy development and library resource utilization. The findings are expected to provide empirical evidence to guide library service improvement, digital skills training, and educational policy formulation in Nigerian universities. The study is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the statement of the problem, Section 3 describes the research methodology, Section 4 presents the results, Section 5 discusses the findings, and Section 6 provides the conclusion, recommendations, and limitations of the study.

Conceptual framework

This study is anchored on Ng's (2012) Digital Literacy Framework, which provides a comprehensive explanation of the skills required for effective participation in a digital information environment. The framework conceptualizes digital literacy as the ability to locate, understand, evaluate, use, and communicate information through digital technologies. It emphasizes that

digital literacy is not limited to basic technical ability but involves a combination of operational, cognitive, and critical skills that enable individuals to function effectively in technology-driven academic and social environments. Ng (2012) identifies digital literacy as comprising three interrelated dimensions: technical or operational skills, cognitive or information-processing skills, and socio-emotional or communicative skills. The technical dimension refers to the ability to operate digital devices and applications such as computers, mobile devices, and software tools. In the context of this study, this includes students' ability to use digital devices effectively for academic tasks, access online databases, and apply software such as word processing tools in their academic work.

The cognitive dimension involves the ability to search for, evaluate, and critically analyze digital information. This is particularly important in academic settings where students are required to distinguish between credible and non-credible sources, synthesize information from multiple platforms, and apply retrieved knowledge to academic tasks. In this study, this dimension relates directly to students' ability to evaluate online information credibility and manage the large volume of digital information available to them through academic databases and the internet.

The socio-emotional or communicative dimension focuses on the ability to communicate and collaborate effectively using digital platforms. This includes the use of email, learning management systems, and other digital communication tools for academic interaction and knowledge sharing. It also reflects how students engage with peers and instructors in digital learning environments, which may influence their overall digital literacy development.

In relation to this study, Ng's Digital Literacy Framework provides a useful lens for understanding how undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti acquire and apply digital literacy skills. It explains that digital literacy is developed through a combination of formal education, personal experience, peer interaction, and continuous practice. These factors collectively influence students' ability to effectively use digital and library resources for academic purposes.

Furthermore, the framework establishes a direct relationship between digital literacy skills and information utilization behaviour. Students who possess higher levels of digital literacy are more likely to effectively access, evaluate, and utilize both digital and physical library resources. Conversely, limited digital literacy skills may result in difficulties in navigating electronic databases, inefficient use of library services, and underutilization of available academic resources.

This framework therefore provides the theoretical foundation for examining the relationship between digital literacy skills and library resource utilization in this study. It guides the interpretation of key variables such as students' ability to use digital tools, their patterns of library usage, and the factors influencing both digital literacy development and resource utilization. By applying Ng's framework, the study is able to situate its findings within a broader understanding of digital competence and academic information behavior in higher education.

Statement of the Problem

In contemporary higher education, undergraduate students are expected to possess adequate digital literacy skills that enable them to effectively access, evaluate and utilize information resources for academic purposes. Universities and academic libraries are increasingly integrating digital technologies and electronic information resources into teaching, learning and research processes in order to enhance students' academic performance and independent learning abilities (Ng, 2012). Consequently, university libraries are expected to provide accessible and user-friendly information resources, while students are expected to demonstrate the digital competencies required for effective utilization of such resources. Recent studies have shown that many undergraduate students in universities still experience challenges relating to digital literacy and effective utilization of library resources. Yila (2024) reported that undergraduate students' use of digital information resources is significantly influenced by their level of digital literacy, suggesting that deficiencies in digital skills can limit effective access to academic information resources. Recent studies have shown that although undergraduate students increasingly use electronic information resources, differences persist in their digital literacy competencies and ability to maximize library resources for academic purposes. Baro, Obaro, and Edem (2019) observed that variations in digital literacy skills significantly influence the effective use of electronic resources in university libraries. Similarly, Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) noted that limited digital competencies affect users' ability to effectively navigate and utilize online information resources. Fakunle et al. (2022) further reported that gaps in digital literacy skills continue to hinder effective library use among undergraduate students despite growing exposure to digital technologies.

Although previous studies have examined digital literacy and electronic resource utilization in different institutions, there is still limited empirical evidence specifically focusing on undergraduate students of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti. In particular, there is inadequate context-specific information regarding the level of digital literacy among students, their patterns of library resource utilization, and the factors influencing both variables within the university environment. This knowledge gap makes it difficult for university management and library administrators to design targeted interventions, improve user education programmes, and enhance library services to meet students' academic and information needs effectively. If these issues remain inadequately addressed, undergraduate students may continue to experience difficulties in accessing and utilizing relevant academic information resources, thereby affecting their research abilities, academic performance and overall learning outcomes. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate digital literacy and the utilization of library resources among undergraduate students of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.

Research questions

1. What is the prevailing level of digital literacy skills use among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

2. What are the patterns of library resource usage among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?
3. What are the factors that influence the development of digital literacy skills among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?
4. What are the factors that influence the utilisation of library resources among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

Objectives of the study

1. Evaluate the prevailing level of digital literacy skills use among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.
2. Investigate the patterns of library resource usage among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.
3. Identify the factors that influence the development of digital literacy skills among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.
4. Determine the factors influencing the utilization of library resources among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.

Research methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was considered appropriate because the study aimed to examine the existing level of digital literacy and library resource utilization among undergraduate students without manipulating any variables. Unlike experimental or correlational designs, the descriptive survey design enabled the researcher to collect data on students' experiences, behaviours, and perceptions as they naturally occur. The population of the study comprised all undergraduate students of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti during the 2024/2025 academic session. According to records from the Academic Affairs Division, the undergraduate population was approximately 22,994 students. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula at a 0.05 level of significance, which produced a sample size of approximately 393 students. To account for non-response and incomplete questionnaires, 420 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 405 were validly completed and used for analysis, representing a 96.4% response rate. A stratified random sampling technique was employed. The population was stratified based on faculty and level of study to ensure proportional representation. Thereafter, respondents were randomly selected from each stratum. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Digital Literacy and Library Resource Utilization Questionnaire (DLLRUQ). The instrument contained sections on demographic information, digital literacy skills, and library resource utilization. The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by experts in Library and Information Science and Educational Measurement. A pilot study involving 30 students from another university was conducted, and the reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's

Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.85. Data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean scores, and standard deviations. Responses were rated on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). A benchmark mean of 2.50 was used for decision-making; mean scores of 2.50 and above were regarded as “Agreed,” while scores below 2.50 were regarded as “Disagreed.”

Analysis

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Table with 3 columns: Category, Frequency, and Percentage. Rows include Gender (Male, Female, Total), Age (15-19, 20-24, 25 & above, Total), Faculty (Agricultural Science, Arts, Basic Medical Sciences, Clinical Sciences, Education, Petroleum, Engineering, Law, Management Sciences, Sciences, Social Sciences, Total), and Academic Level (100 Level, 200 Level, 300 Level, 400 Level, 500 Level, Total).

The demographic data show that out of the 405 respondents, 228 (56.3%) were female, while 177 (43.7%) were male. This indicates a higher representation of female respondents in the study. In terms of age, the majority of respondents, 197 (48.6%), were between 15 and 19 years, followed

by 130 (32.1%) within the age range of 20–24 years, while 78 (19.3%) were aged 25 years and above.

The respondents were drawn from eleven faculties to ensure broad representation across the university. The Faculty of Education recorded the highest proportion of respondents with 55 (13.6%), followed by Management Sciences with 51 (12.6%) and Law with 46 (11.4%). Petroleum Engineering had the lowest representation with 12 respondents (2.9%). The faculty classifications used in this study reflect the official academic structure of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti.

Regarding academic level, 102 respondents (25.2%) were in 100 Level, 98 (24.2%) were in 300 Level, 80 (19.8%) were in 200 Level, 78 (19.3%) were in 400 Level, while 47 respondents (11.6%) were in 500 Level. This indicates that respondents were fairly distributed across the different levels of study.

Analysis of Research questions

RQ1: What is the prevailing level of digital literacy skills use among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

Table 2: Level of Digital Literacy Skills Use among Undergraduates

Table with 7 columns: Level of Digital Literacy, SA (%), A (%), D (%), SD (%), Mean, S.D. It lists eight statements about digital literacy skills and their corresponding percentages and statistics.

Decision Benchmark: Mean scores of 2.50 and above were regarded as “Agreed,” while mean scores below 2.50 were regarded as “Disagreed.”

The findings in Table 2 indicate that undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti generally possess moderate to high digital literacy skills. A large majority of respondents (90.4%) agreed that they use digital devices effectively for academic tasks, with a corresponding mean score of 3.39, which is above the benchmark mean of 2.50. Similarly, 71.8% of respondents indicated that they frequently use the internet to search for academic information, while 92.6% reported that they could evaluate the credibility of online information sources. These findings suggest that many students possess functional and evaluative digital literacy skills.

However, the findings also reveal weaknesses in some aspects of digital literacy. Although 52.6% of respondents agreed that they were comfortable using digital tools such as word processing software, the mean score of 2.40 fell below the benchmark mean of 2.50. This indicates that respondents’ level of confidence in the practical use of certain academic digital tools was relatively low despite the slight majority agreement. In addition, respondents reported experiencing difficulties when using digital devices for academic tasks, as reflected by a mean score of 2.45.

The findings further show that 96.3% of respondents believed that improving their digital literacy skills would enhance their academic performance, with the item recording the highest mean score of 3.55. This suggests that students recognize the importance of digital literacy in academic success.

These findings align with Ng’s (2012) digital literacy framework, which emphasizes that digital literacy extends beyond basic access to technology to include technical, cognitive, and critical evaluation skills necessary for effective academic engagement. The results therefore suggest that while students demonstrate competence in basic digital and information-searching activities, gaps still exist in advanced practical and academic digital skills.

Research Question 2:

What are the patterns of library resource usage among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

Table 3: Patterns of Library Resource Usage

Patterns of Library Resource Usage	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	S.D
I visit the university library regularly to access resources for my studies	86 (21.2)	312 (77.0)	0 (0.0)	7 (1.7)	3.18	0.50

Patterns of Library Resource Usage	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	S.D
I use physical books from the library for academic research	126 (31.1)	221 (54.6)	53 (13.1)	5 (1.2)	3.16	0.68
I find it easy to access the library’s online databases	86 (21.2)	283 (69.9)	30 (7.4)	6 (1.5)	3.11	0.58
I have attended library workshops or training sessions to improve my research skills	107 (26.4)	249 (61.5)	44 (10.9)	5 (1.2)	3.13	0.64
I am satisfied with the variety of resources available at the university library	0 (0.0)	284 (70.1)	114 (28.1)	7 (1.7)	2.68	0.50
I face obstacles when trying to access certain library resources	9 (2.2)	253 (62.5)	141 (34.8)	2 (0.5)	2.66	0.53
Recommendations from lecturers influence my decision to use specific library resources	9 (2.2)	285 (70.4)	106 (26.2)	5 (1.2)	2.74	0.51
I am confident in my ability to navigate the library’s physical and digital resources effectively	76 (18.8)	269 (66.4)	54 (13.3)	6 (1.5)	3.02	0.62

Decision Benchmark: Mean scores of 2.50 and above were regarded as “Agreed,” while mean scores below 2.50 were regarded as “Disagreed.”

The findings in Table 3 indicate that undergraduate students demonstrate a high level of engagement with both the physical and digital resources of the university library. A majority of respondents (98.2%) agreed that they regularly visit the university library to access resources for their studies, with a mean score of 3.18. Similarly, 85.7% of respondents indicated that they use physical books for academic research, suggesting that printed materials remain relevant despite the increasing availability of digital resources.

The findings further revealed that 91.1% of respondents found it easy to access the library’s online databases, while 87.9% had attended library workshops or training sessions aimed at improving research skills. These results suggest that students actively engage with both digital library services and user education programmes provided by the university library.

However, the findings also indicate some challenges in library resource utilization. Although respondents generally expressed satisfaction with the variety of library resources available (mean = 2.68), a notable proportion of students reported facing obstacles when attempting to access certain resources, as reflected in the mean score of 2.66. This implies that accessibility and availability issues may still affect effective library use among some students.

In addition, lecturer recommendations were found to influence students’ use of library resources, with 72.6% of respondents agreeing that lecturers guide their selection and use of academic

materials. This highlights the important role of academic staff in promoting library resource utilization among undergraduates.

Research Question Three:

What are the factors influencing the development of digital literacy skills among undergraduates at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

Table 4: Factors Influencing Digital Literacy Development

Development of Digital Literacy Skills	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	S.D
Formal education such as courses and workshops helped me to improve my digital literacy skills	48 (11.9)	219 (54.1)	108 (26.7)	30 (7.4)	2.70	0.77
Personal experience with digital devices contributed to my digital literacy development	96 (23.7)	225 (55.6)	84 (20.7)	0 (0.0)	3.03	0.67
Interactions with peers are valuable in enhancing my digital literacy skills	117 (28.9)	132 (32.6)	96 (23.7)	60 (14.8)	2.76	1.03
Integrating digital literacy into the curriculum is essential for enhancing students' digital skills	144 (35.6)	186 (45.9)	75 (18.5)	0 (0.0)	3.17	0.72
I feel motivated to improve my digital literacy skills through self-directed learning	48 (11.9)	258 (63.7)	69 (17.0)	30 (7.4)	2.80	0.74
I face challenges in finding resources to improve my digital literacy skills	126 (31.1)	195 (48.1)	54 (13.3)	30 (7.4)	3.03	0.86
I believe digital literacy skills are crucial for success in both academic and professional contexts	18 (4.4)	318 (78.5)	30 (7.4)	39 (9.6)	2.78	0.67

The data in Table 4 show that the development of digital literacy skills among undergraduate students is influenced by a combination of formal education, personal experience, peer interaction, curriculum integration, and self-directed learning. A majority of respondents (66.0%) agreed that formal education such as courses and workshops contributes to their digital literacy development, with a mean score of 2.70. This suggests that structured academic exposure plays a meaningful role, although it is not the sole driver of digital competence. This finding implies that classroom-based instruction alone may not be sufficient without complementary experiential learning opportunities. Similarly, 79.3% of respondents indicated that personal experience with digital devices contributes significantly to their digital literacy development, with a mean score of 3.03. This suggests that informal, hands-on engagement with technology is a stronger driver of digital literacy than formal instruction in some cases. This aligns with the idea that digital skills are often acquired through repeated use and practice rather than classroom teaching alone.

Peer interaction was also identified as an influencing factor, with 61.5% of respondents agreeing that learning from peers enhances their digital literacy skills. However, the relatively higher standard deviation (1.03) suggests variability in how students benefit from peer learning, indicating that peer influence may not be equally effective across all learners. A strong consensus was observed regarding curriculum integration, with 81.5% of respondents agreeing that embedding digital literacy into academic programmes is essential. This reflects a perception that digital literacy should be formally embedded within academic content rather than treated as an optional skill. In addition, 75.6% of respondents reported motivation to improve their digital literacy through self-directed learning, indicating that students are not entirely dependent on formal instruction and are willing to engage in independent skill development. However, the data also show that students face challenges in accessing resources to improve their digital literacy skills, with 79.2% acknowledging such difficulties. This suggests that while motivation exists, institutional and environmental constraints may limit effective skill development.

Research Question 4: What factors influence the utilization of library resources among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti?

Table 5: Factors Influencing Library Resource Utilization

Table with 7 columns: Factors Influencing Library Resource Utilization, SA (%), A (%), D (%), SD (%), Mean, S.D. It lists various factors like 'My motivation to utilize library resources is influenced by the relevance of the resources to my studies' and 'Accessibility (e.g., physical location and online access) plays a significant role in my decision to use library resources'.

Decision Benchmark: Mean scores of 2.50 and above were regarded as “Agreed,” while mean scores below 2.50 were regarded as “Disagreed.”

The findings in Table 5 show that several factors influence the utilization of library resources among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti. A majority of respondents (80.7%) agreed that the relevance of library resources to their studies motivates their use of such resources, with a mean score of 2.98. This suggests that students are more likely to utilize library materials that directly support their academic activities.

Accessibility was also identified as an important factor influencing library use. Although 55.5% of respondents agreed that physical location and online access affect their utilization of library resources, a considerable proportion of respondents indicated otherwise, suggesting that some students may still experience access-related challenges. This is further supported by the finding that 66.0% of respondents reported encountering barriers when trying to access certain library resources.

The findings further revealed that recommendations from lecturers and peers significantly influence students’ utilization of library resources, as 79.3% of respondents agreed that such recommendations encourage them to use specific materials. In addition, 66.7% of respondents expressed satisfaction with the assistance provided by library staff, indicating that library personnel contribute positively to students’ use of resources.

Despite these positive findings, respondents also reported challenges in locating needed resources. A large proportion of students (80.7%) agreed that they often experience frustration when searching for specific materials in the library, suggesting possible issues relating to resource organization, retrieval systems, or user navigation skills.

Furthermore, 57.7% of respondents believed that effective utilization of library resources enhances academic performance, with a mean score of 2.58 on a 4-point scale. Although the mean score is above the benchmark of 2.50, it is relatively lower compared to other items, indicating that some students may not yet fully recognize or maximize the academic benefits associated with effective library resource utilization.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study on digital literacy and library resource utilization among undergraduate students at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti indicate that students possess generally moderate to high levels of digital engagement, but still experience notable skill gaps that affect optimal academic use of digital and library resources. The results further suggest that while access to technology is widespread, the depth of effective and confident use varies across different dimensions of digital literacy.

The study revealed that a large proportion of students (90.3%) reported effective use of digital devices for academic tasks. This aligns with contemporary literature suggesting that university students are increasingly immersed in digital environments due to the integration of ICT into teaching and learning. However, as Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014) argue, access does not automatically translate into meaningful digital skills. The present findings support this argument, as students may be frequent users of digital tools but not necessarily proficient in all academic applications.

Despite the high usage of digital devices, only 52.6% of respondents reported comfort in using essential academic tools such as word processing software, with a mean score below the acceptance threshold (2.40). This indicates a practical skill gap in operational digital literacy. This finding is consistent with Oyedokun-Ojo et al. (2018), who observed that university students in developing contexts often demonstrate strong social use of technology but weaker proficiency in productivity and academic software applications. This gap may be attributed to insufficient hands-on training in digital tool application within academic programmes.

The study also found that 71.8% of respondents frequently use the internet for academic information, while 92.6% can evaluate online information credibility. This suggests relatively strong information literacy skills, particularly in source evaluation. However, 71.1% of respondents also reported feeling overwhelmed by the volume of digital information available. This reflects what Leu et al. (2015) describe as “information overload,” where students struggle not with access, but with filtering and managing excessive information. It therefore indicates that cognitive management skills remain a challenge even when evaluative skills are present.

Regarding library resource utilization, the findings show a very high level of engagement, with 98.2% of students reporting regular library use and 91.1% accessing online databases. This demonstrates that both physical and digital library systems remain central to academic work. This is particularly important in contexts like Nigerian universities, where infrastructural constraints often necessitate blended reliance on both print and electronic resources (Ani & Bassey, 2017). The dual usage pattern observed suggests that students are adapting to a hybrid information environment.

However, despite this high usage, 64.7% of respondents indicated they face obstacles when accessing library resources, while about 28.1% expressed dissatisfaction with the variety of available materials. These findings suggest that access does not always equate to satisfaction or efficiency. Similar observations were made by Baro, Onyenania, and Osaheni (2019), who reported that limitations in database coverage, poor search skills, and infrastructural constraints often hinder effective library resource utilization in Nigerian universities.

The study also found that 72.6% of respondents were influenced by lecturers’ recommendations in their use of library resources. This highlights the continued importance of academic staff in shaping students’ information behaviour. Rather than relying solely on librarians, students often

depend on lecturers as academic gatekeepers who guide resource selection. This finding extends the information behaviour model by Case and Given (2016), which emphasizes the role of social influence in information-seeking decisions.

Overall, the findings suggest that while students demonstrate high exposure to digital and library resources, there is still a gap between access and effective utilization. This supports the theoretical position of Van Deursen and Van Dijk (2014), which distinguishes between operational, information, and strategic digital skills. The results of this study indicate that operational access is relatively strong, but strategic and productive use of digital and library tools still requires improvement.

Conclusion

This study examined digital literacy skills and the utilization of library resources among undergraduate students of Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti, in line with four research questions. The study found that students generally demonstrate high engagement with digital devices and the internet for academic purposes, as well as strong ability to evaluate online information. However, gaps remain in practical digital competencies, particularly in the use of academic tools such as word processing software, indicating uneven development of operational digital literacy skills. The study further revealed that students make extensive use of both physical and digital library resources. Regular library visits and frequent use of online databases indicate strong engagement with library services. However, challenges such as difficulties in locating resources and limited satisfaction with resource variety suggest that access and usability issues still exist within the library system.

It was also established from the study that digital literacy development among students is influenced by multiple factors, including formal education, personal experience with digital devices, and peer interactions. These findings indicate that digital literacy acquisition is shaped by both structured academic exposure and informal learning environments. The research identified that library resource utilization is influenced by factors such as resource relevance, accessibility, lecturer recommendations, and perceived academic benefits. However, barriers in access and navigation still affect optimal use of library resources, showing that availability does not always translate into effective utilization.

Therefore, the study concludes that while undergraduate students possess functional digital and library resource engagement skills, gaps still exist between access, competence, and effective utilization. These gaps highlight the need for targeted interventions to strengthen both digital literacy competencies and library service effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The university should implement targeted digital literacy training programmes focusing on practical academic tools such as word processing software, reference management tools, and academic databases to improve students' operational digital skills.
2. Training programmes should be introduced to help students develop information management and digital overload coping strategies, including skills for filtering, organizing, and evaluating large volumes of digital information effectively.
3. The university library should expand both print and electronic collections, particularly in specialized and emerging academic fields, to ensure resources adequately meet students' academic needs.
4. Efforts should be made to improve ease of access to library resources, including upgrading digital infrastructure, improving search systems, and enhancing the physical organization of library materials to reduce user frustration.
5. Faculty members should be actively involved in integrating and recommending library resources within course instruction, to guide students toward relevant and high-quality academic materials.
6. The university library should not only expand workshops but also regularly evaluate and update the quality, content, and effectiveness of existing user training programmes, ensuring they align with students' evolving digital and academic needs.

Limitations of the study

1. The study employed a cross-sectional survey design, which limits the ability to establish causal relationships between digital literacy and library resource utilization.
2. Data were based on self-reported responses, which may be influenced by bias, overestimation, or underestimation of actual abilities and usage patterns.
3. The study was restricted to Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti alone, which limits the generalizability of findings to other universities with different infrastructural and academic contexts.
4. The analysis relied primarily on descriptive statistics, meaning that predictive or inferential relationships between variables were not examined.
5. The study did not incorporate qualitative data (e.g., interviews or focus groups), which could have provided deeper insights into students' lived experiences and challenges.

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